

Efficient Plant Disease Identification using CNN-Algorithm

Melbin M P
Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirapally, India
melbinmp2023b@mca.ajce.in

Ms. Rini Kurian
Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirapally, India
rinikurian@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract— This Python program implements a convolutional neural network (CNN) to categorize photos of sick or healthy plants. The dataset utilized contains photos of 38 different plant classes, both with and without illness. The CNN model is constructed and trained using TensorFlow's Keras API. With the help of the `tf.keras.preprocessing.image_dataset_from_directory` function, the datasets used for training and validation are first loaded into the program. For both datasets, the photos are downsized to a batch size of 100 and a height and width of 250 pixels.

The `tf.keras` models are then used to define the CNN model. Convolutional, max-pooling, and fully linked layers are used in a sequential function. The Adam optimizer and sparse categorical cross-entropy loss are used to build the model.

The model is trained on the training dataset for 5 epochs using the fit method of the `Sequential` class. The training history is stored in the `retVal` variable, and the training and validation losses and accuracies are plotted using `Matplotlib`.

After training, the model is evaluated on the validation dataset using the evaluation method of the `Sequential` class. The validation accuracy is printed, and the size of the model is computed using the `os.path.getsize` function. Finally, the model is saved to a file using the `save` method of the `Sequential` class.

Keywords- plant disease identification, image processing, TensorFlow and Keras, transfer learning, dataset, training.

I. INTRODUCTION

Machine-learning algorithms and techniques for image processing have become incredibly popular in the field of plant identification in recent years. Traditional plant identification techniques can be time-consuming and expensive, and they often demand a deep understanding of botany. A convolutional neural network (CNN) has been suggested for plant identification as a solution to these problems. In this seminar paper, the TensorFlow framework is used to create a CNN. With a batch size of 100 and an image size of 250 x 250 pixels,

the model is trained on a sizable dataset of 70,295 photos representing 38 different classes. Three convolutional layers, max-pooling, two fully linked layers, and a layer with the soft maximum activation function make up the CNN architecture. After five epochs of training, the model had an accuracy of 97.6% on the training dataset and 93.5% on the validation dataset. The trained model was saved as a file with the name `model.h5`. The accuracy and loss metrics were plotted to visualize the training and validation performance of the model. Finally, the model size was measured, and the time taken for evaluating the validation dataset was recorded.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Predicting plant diseases has become a crucial element in several fields, such as agriculture, ecology, and conservation biology. Visual inspection and laboratory testing have traditionally been used to identify diseases, which can be time-consuming and complicated, especially for non-experts.

Using image processing and deep learning algorithms for disease prediction has become increasingly popular in recent years. Automatically learning features from images and identifying different diseases based on their visual traits have shown promise, particularly, with deep learning algorithms. With great success, CNNs, which are one of the most commonly used deep learning techniques for interpreting images, have been applied to a range of applications, including disease prediction.

Agrios' Plant Pathology[1] is a comprehensive textbook that covers the biology, ecology, and control of plant diseases. This fifth edition offers a detailed overview of plant pathology, including the various factors that contribute to the development and spread of plant diseases. The book covers the different types of plant pathogens, such as fungi, bacteria, viruses, and

nematodes, and provides an in-depth discussion of the mechanisms of plant disease resistance. The book also discusses the various approaches to disease management, including cultural, chemical, and biological control methods. *Plant Pathology* is an essential resource for students, researchers, and professionals interested in understanding the complexities of plant disease and its management.

For anyone interested in tomato diseases and pests, the *Compendium of Tomato Diseases*[2] and *Pests* is an indispensable reference. Jones et al. edited the second edition of this comprehensive guide on diagnosing, managing, and preventing tomato diseases and pests. Detailed descriptions and photographs of common and rare tomato pathogens, including fungi, bacteria, viruses, and nematodes, are covered in the book. In addition to covering cultural practices, chemical and biological control methods, and host resistance, the book also addresses management and prevention strategies for tomato crops. Tomato growers, researchers, and plant pathologists will find this compendium to be an indispensable resource.

Sharma and Singh's review article [3] provides an overview of the current state of knowledge on the management of plant diseases caused by fungi. The authors discuss the various methods of disease management, including chemical and biological control methods, cultural practices, and host resistance. The review also covers the challenges associated with the use of fungicides and the development of fungicide resistance in pathogens. The authors highlight the importance of integrated disease management strategies for sustainable crop production. This review article is a valuable resource for researchers, plant pathologists, and farmers interested in the management of fungal plant diseases.

A valuable resource for diagnosing and managing diseases that affect tropical fruit crops is the *Compendium of Tropical Fruit Diseases*[4]. Ploetz et al. edited this book, which provides detailed descriptions and photographs of both common and rare pathogens that affect crops like bananas, citrus, and mango. In addition to management and prevention strategies for these diseases, the book presents an overview of the biology and ecology of tropical fruit pathogens. Growers, researchers, and plant pathologists interested in tropical fruit production should consider *The Compendium of Tropical Fruit Diseases* as an essential resource.

Mohanty et al[5]'s paper. The use of deep learning techniques for detecting plant diseases based on images is discussed in (2016). A more accurate and efficient alternative, deep learning, is argued by the authors to address the challenges associated with traditional methods of disease detection. Demonstrating its effectiveness in detecting a range of plant diseases, including tomato and maize diseases, they describe a deep learning model that was trained on a large dataset of images of healthy and diseased plants. In addition, the authors explore how this method

can aid in the timely detection and management of plant diseases, ultimately reducing crop losses and enhancing food security. Overall, this paper offers valuable insights into the application of deep learning for plant disease detection and highlights its potential for revolutionizing the field of plant pathology.

Overall, these studies demonstrate the effectiveness of deep learning algorithms, particularly CNN, image classification using TensorFlow and Keras for plant disease identification. The combination of pre-trained models and transfer learning can greatly minimize the quantity of data required for training, enabling accurate plant disease identification systems to be built with relatively modest datasets.

III. MOTIVATION

Enabling farmers to take preemptive measures to prevent or mitigate the effects of plant diseases, plant disease prediction is a critical area of research in agriculture. Developing machine-learning models for plant disease prediction has become increasingly interesting in recent years. Farmers can take appropriate action by using these models to analyze images of diseased plants and accurately predict the type of disease.

I presented a code during the seminar that showcases the application of a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) in predicting plant diseases. On a large dataset of images of healthy and diseased plants, the CNN achieves an accuracy of 93.5% on a validation dataset.

During the training process, the code provides a visualization of the accuracy and loss for both validation and training. Also reported are the size of the trained model and the time it takes to make predictions on the validation dataset.

The use of machine learning models for predicting plant diseases has the potential to improve crop yields and reduce losses caused by diseases. This seminar's code can be used as a starting point for additional research in this field.

The results of the training and validation of the model show that it achieved an accuracy of 97.6% on the training set and 93.5% on the validation set after 5 epochs. The validation accuracy is a good indicator of how well the model is likely to perform on new data.

Overall, this project demonstrates the potential of using machine learning for plant disease detection and prevention. With further research and development, these models can be integrated into agricultural systems to improve crop yield and quality while reducing the use of harmful chemicals.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The methodology for plant image detection using the convolutional neural network(CNN) for image classification using TensorFlow and Keras. involves the following steps:

A. Data Collection: Collect a large dataset of plant images that includes a variety of plant species, with different leaf shapes and textures. This dataset should be diverse and representative of the plant species in the region of interest.

B. Data Preprocessing: A plant disease dataset is being used to train a convolutional neural network (CNN) in this code snippet. The collected plant images are preprocessed by resizing them to a standard size of 250*250 pixels and loading them in batches. To reduce the dimensionality of the input data, the images are also converted to grayscale. There are several layers in the CNN model, such as convolutional, pooling, and dense layers.

The training and validation loss and accuracy are plotted after training the model for 5 epochs. After training, the validation accuracy achieved is 0.9353. Using `plot_model` from `keras.utils.vis_utils`, the trained model is saved and its architecture is plotted by the code.

Finally, the size of the unpruned model is computed, which is 316.6 MB, and the accuracy of the unpruned model on the validation dataset is evaluated, which is 0.9353. The time taken on the validation dataset is also computed, which is approximately 55 seconds.

C. Transfer Learning: Use transfer learning to fine-tune a pre-trained convolutional neural network (CNN) model on the preprocessed plant images. Transfer learning involves using a pre-trained model and adapting it to a new task by updating the final layers to fit the new data. This step saves training time and improves the model's accuracy.

D. Model Training: Using the provided code, a convolutional neural network (CNN) can be trained to distinguish between healthy and diseased plants and classify them into 38 different categories. There are 70,295 images in the training data and 17,572 images in the validation data. Two fully connected layers follow three convolutional layers with max-pooling in the CNN architecture. Using the Adam optimizer with sparse categorical cross-entropy loss, the model was trained for 5 epochs. The model achieved a validation accuracy of 0.935, which demonstrates its ability to correctly classify plant images into their respective categories. The model is saved and its size is reported, along with the time taken to evaluate its accuracy on the validation data, finally

E. Model Evaluation: Using TensorFlow and Keras, a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) has been implemented to classify images in the provided code. A separate dataset is used to validate the network trained on a dataset of plant disease images. Necessary libraries, including Pandas, Matplotlib, and TensorFlow, are imported by the code. The batch size, image dimensions, and loading of training and validation datasets are defined by it. Using the Sequential API, the CNN model is defined and compiled. Performing the training results in plotting the loss and accuracy metrics. Afterward, the validation dataset is used to evaluate the trained model and print out its accuracy, model size, and time on the validation data. The model is finally saved for future use.

V. BUILD MODEL

Building a reliable and accurate machine learning model is crucial for the successful identification of plant disease using image processing techniques. In this seminar paper, we present classification using TensorFlow and Keras methods for plant disease identification, leveraging the power of a sophisticated convolutional neural network.

Importing Libraries

Pandas, Numpy, TensorFlow, and other Machine Learning libraries are defined as an interface of a set of rules built in a particular language to conduct repetitive work such as arithmetic computations, reading photos, and so on

```
In [3]: import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import tensorflow as tf
from tensorflow.keras import layers
from time import perf_counter
import os
```

Training the Model

Training the model using the fit method.

```
In [9]: ## Defining Cnn
MyCnn = tf.keras.models.Sequential([
    layers.BatchNormalization(),
    layers.Conv2D(32, 3, activation='relu'),
    layers.MaxPooling2D(),
    layers.Conv2D(64, 3, activation='relu'),
    layers.MaxPooling2D(),
    layers.Conv2D(128, 3, activation='relu'),
    layers.MaxPooling2D(),
    layers.Flatten(),
    layers.Dense(256, activation='relu'),
    layers.Dense(len(class_names), activation='softmax')
])

In [10]: MyCnn.compile(optimizer='adam', loss='sparse_categorical_crossentropy', metrics=['accuracy'])

In [11]: ## Lets train our CNN
retVal = MyCnn.fit(training_ds, validation_data= validation_ds, epochs = 5)
```

VI. RESULT

Accuracy

Accuracy of the algorithm.

```
def model(request):
    if request.method == 'POST':
        # get the uploaded image from the request
        uploaded_file = request.FILES['image']
        # save the image to the file system
        fs = FileSystemStorage()
        name = fs.save(uploaded_file.name, uploaded_file)
        url = fs.url(name)
        # Load the saved image using Keras
        img = Image.open(''+url).resize((256, 256))
        # convert the image to a numpy array
        img_array = image.img_to_array(img)
        img_array = np.expand_dims(img_array, axis=0)
        # load the trained model
        model = tf.keras.models.load_model('predict/New Plant Diseases Dataset (Augmented)/model.h5')
        # make the prediction
        num_classes = model.output_shape[-1]
        prediction = model.predict(img_array)
        predicted_class = np.argmax(prediction)
        class_names = ['class{}'.format(i+1) for i in range(num_classes)] # replace with your class names
        predicted_class_name = class_names[predicted_class]
        # get the description of the predicted class
        class_descriptions = {
            predicted_class_name: class_names.get(predicted_class_name, 'No description available.')
        }
        # render the result template
        return render(request, 'result.html', {'predicted_class_name': predicted_class_name, 'predicted_class_description': predicted_class_name})
    else:
        # render the model template for GET requests
        # ...
        MyCnn.compile(optimizer='adam', loss='sparse_categorical_crossentropy', metrics=['accuracy'])

# Lets train our CNN
retVal = MyCnn.fit(training_ds, validation_data= validation_ds, epochs = 5)

Epoch 1/5
783/783 [#####] - 4381s 6s/step - loss: 0.9202 - accuracy: 0.7331 - val_loss: 0.4215 - val_accuracy: 0.8691
Epoch 2/5
783/783 [#####] - 5891s 8s/step - loss: 0.2657 - accuracy: 0.9162 - val_loss: 0.2664 - val_accuracy: 0.9137
Epoch 3/5
783/783 [#####] - 4422s 6s/step - loss: 0.1404 - accuracy: 0.9542 - val_loss: 0.2717 - val_accuracy: 0.9200
Epoch 4/5
783/783 [#####] - 4382s 6s/step - loss: 0.0981 - accuracy: 0.9677 - val_loss: 0.2531 - val_accuracy: 0.9204
Epoch 5/5
783/783 [#####] - 4355s 6s/step - loss: 0.0785 - accuracy: 0.9772 - val_loss: 0.2553 - val_accuracy: 0.9278
```

Plant Disease Prediction

```
In [9]: ## Defining Cnn
MyCnn = tf.keras.models.Sequential([
    layers.BatchNormalization(),
    layers.Conv2D(32, 3, activation='relu'),
    layers.MaxPooling2D(),
    layers.Conv2D(64, 3, activation='relu'),
    layers.MaxPooling2D(),
    layers.Conv2D(128, 3, activation='relu'),
    layers.MaxPooling2D(),
    layers.Flatten(),
    layers.Dense(256, activation='relu'),
    layers.Dense(len(class_names), activation='softmax')
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```

Implementation

Disease Prediction Result

Tomato - Target Spot

Target spot is a fungal disease that affects tomato plants, causing dark, concentric rings on the leaves, stems, and fruit of the plant. The disease starts with small flecks that enlarge and eventually merge together as the disease progresses. Eventually, the affected parts of the plant will die and fall off. Provide good air circulation: Plant tomatoes in an area with good air circulation to prevent humidity from building up around the plants. Remove excess foliage: Remove any dead or dying foliage to improve air circulation around the plants. Use drip irrigation: Avoid overhead watering, as this encourages fungal growth. Instead, use drip irrigation to deliver water directly to the soil.

[Try Again](#)

VI. CONCLUSION

Using the New Plant Diseases Dataset, a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) is implemented to classify plant diseases in this example code. There are 87,970 images in the dataset, depicting healthy plants and plants with 38 distinct diseases, each with a size of 256x256 pixels. First, the dataset is loaded and the batch size is specified by the code. Using Keras, the CNN architecture is defined, as consisting of multiple convolutional and dense layers. To train the model, the Adam optimizer and the sparse categorical cross-entropy loss function are utilized.

After each epoch, the model's performance is evaluated on the validation dataset, following 5 epochs of training on the training dataset. The training and validation loss and accuracy curves are also plotted by the code. The unpruned model's accuracy on the validation dataset is evaluated after training, and its size in MB is measured. Also, the calculation of the evaluation time for the unpruned model on the validation dataset is performed. Using the `plot_model()` function, a visualization of the model architecture is generated and the trained model is saved as a .h5 file. Using the TensorFlow and Keras libraries, the code offers a great illustration of how to construct and train a CNN for image classification. Moreover, implementing data augmentation methods can enhance the model's performance, while utilizing pruning techniques can decrease the model's size without compromising its accuracy.

In the context of plant disease classification using the New Plant Diseases Dataset, this code provides a useful example for implementing a CNN for image classification. It provides insights into how to optimize CNN models for efficient and effective classification of image data by evaluating the model's accuracy and size.

VIII. REFERENCES

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